

Diagnostic Accuracy of Serum Ascites Albumin Gradient (SAAG) with Ascitic Fluid Total Protein (AFTP) in Determining the Etiopathogenesis of Ascites

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Abstract:

Introduction: The differential diagnosis of ascites remains difficult in clinical practice due to its varied etiopathogenesis. The serum-ascites albumin gradient (SAAG) is a better way to classify ascites than the total protein concentration of the fluid. We undertook the present study to assess the serum ascitic fluid albumin gradient (SAAG) in ascites cases and to compare its usefulness in determining the cause of ascites with the ascitic fluid total protein (AFTP) levels.

Material and Methods: A total of 102 patients who had no prior etiology diagnosis of ascites were recruited. Participants had abdominal USG and CT scans to determine the presence of ascites and concurrently obtained ascitic fluid and blood samples, testing them for total protein, and serum albumin. We analysed serum albumin, ascitic fluid albumin, total protein, and the serum-ascitic fluid albumin gradient.

Results: The commonest cause was cirrhosis (56.86%), followed by congestive cardiac failure (CCF) (18.62%), TB ascites (15.68%). SAAG levels were significantly associated with cirrhosis and congestive cardiac failure. SAAG has a sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy of 86.22%, 85.78%, 95.36%, 67.12%, and 88.34% respectively. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy of SAAG in relation to AFTP were all 65.74%, 62.32%, 32.76%, 86.20%, and 63%, respectively.

Conclusion: SAAG was more sensitive and specific in determining the underlying pathophysiology of ascites. Comparison of SAAG and AFTP's diagnostic accuracy revealed that SAAG significantly outperformed AFTP.

Keywords: Serum ascitic fluid albumin gradient (SAAG), Ascitic fluid total protein (AFTP), Cirrhosis, Ascites.

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Introduction

Ascites is a pathological condition in which extracellular fluid accumulates in the peritoneal cavity. Both diagnostic and therapeutic abdominal paracentesis are often required for refractory ascites [1]. Determine the cause of ascites quickly and affordably using abdominal paracentesis and appropriate ascitic fluid analysis. Transudate or exudate has historically been used to categorize ascites, with a cut-off value of 2.5 gm% for ascitic fluid total protein.

Ascites is typically a transudate in patients with hepatic cirrhosis. However, the decision-making process may be complicated by the fact that up to 20% of these people may develop exudative ascites [2]. Numerous studies have shown that the serum ascitic fluid albumin gradient (SAAG) is a more

effective way to classify ascites than the ascitic fluid total protein (AFTP) concentration and other criteria. The SAAG has a direct correlation with portal pressure and is based on oncotic hydrostatic balance [3]. The ascitic fluid was split into two groups based on the difference in the amounts of ascitic albumin and serum. People with portal hypertension had a gradient >1.1 g/dl, while people with ascites had a gradient <1.1 g/dl.

The drawbacks of the SAAG include the difficulty distinguishing between ascites from TB and malignancy, ascites produced by non-alcoholic cirrhosis, and mixed etiological diseases [5-7]. A comparison of the diagnostic accuracy of AFTP and SAAG in determining the pathophysiology of ascites is required due to their respective

limitations. This will assist in determining the underlying etiology of ascites in a range of illnesses, both hepatic and non-hepatic. With above reference this study was designed to evaluate serum ascitic fluid albumin gradient with ascitic fluid total protein in ascites cases with hepatic and non-hepatic causes.

Material and Methods

This observational study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine at Maheshwara Medical College and Hospital, Isnapur, Patancheru from June 2022 to April 2024. A total of 102 patients who visited and were hospitalized at the Department of General Medicine but had no prior etiology diagnosis were enrolled.

Cases with a history of ascites, normal coagulation profile, and willingness to participate were considered. Cases with severe coagulopathy, ascites with hepatic encephalopathy, acute gastrointestinal bleeding, a history of diuretic medication prior to ascites fluid analysis, and refusal to participate were excluded. The

institutional ethics committee approved the study procedure, and the research participants provided written informed permission.

We conducted a full clinical and physical examination on all subjects and obtained their entire medical history. Participants had abdominal USG and CT scans to determine the presence of ascites. We concurrently obtained ascitic fluid and blood samples, testing them for albumin, total protein, and serum albumin. We computed ascitic fluid albumin and serum albumin using the Bromo Cresol Green technique and determined the ascitic fluid total protein using the Biuret method [9].

We assessed serum albumin, ascitic fluid albumin, total protein, and the serum-ascitic fluid albumin gradient. We analyzed the acquired data using SPSS 26.0. We expressed continuous variables using mean and standard deviation. ANOVA was performed to determine the significance of the research parameters. $P < 0.05$ was deemed statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of cases as per Sociodemographic characteristics.

Parameters	Total no of cases (n=102)	
	Frequency	Percentage
Age (In years)		
Below 21	02	1.96%
21-30	12	11.76%
31-40	13	12.74%
41-50	28	27.45%
51-60	32	31.37%
61-70	14	13.72%
>70	01	0.98%
Gender		
Male	67	65.68%
Female	35	34.31%
Etiological distribution		
Cirrhosis	58	56.86%
TB ascites	16	15.68%
CCF	19	18.62%
Peritoneal carcinomatosis	05	4.90%
Hypothyroidism	03	2.94%
Liver metastasis	01	0.98%

Graph 1: Distribution of cases as per AFTP levels

Graph 2: Distribution of cases as per SAAG levels

Table 2: Classification of ascites in connection with etiology and SAAG and AFTP levels

Etiology	SAAG levels			AFTP levels		
	<1.1 gm/dl	>1.1 gm/dl	P-value	<2.5 gm/dl	>2.5 gm/dl	p-value
Cirrhosis (n=58)	10	48	0.018	32	26	0.001
TB ascites (n=16)	13	03	0.782	06	10	0.016
CCF (n=19)	04	15	0.001	05	14	0.042
Peritoneal carcinomatosis (n=5)	03	02	1.290	01	04	0.018
Hypothyroidism (n=3)	-	03	0.937	02	01	1.722
Liver metastasis (n=1)	-	01	0.895	01	-	0.946

Table 3: Mean levels of study parameters

Parameters	Mean \pm SD
Serum albumin	2.89 \pm 0.74
Ascitic fluid albumin	1.41 \pm 0.54
AFTP	2.49 \pm 1.02
SAAG	1.43 \pm 0.657

Table 4: Diagnostic accuracy of SAAG and AFTP.

Parameters	SAAG	AFTP
Sensitivity	86.22%	65.74%
Specificity	85.78%	62.32%
Positive predictive value	95.36%	32.76%
Negative predictive value	67.12%	86.20%
Diagnostic accuracy	88.34%	63%

Discussion

The majority of participants were between the ages of 51 and 60 (31.37%) and 41 and 50 (27.45%), with a 65.68% male predominance. The most common cause was cirrhosis (56.86%), followed by congestive cardiac failure (CCF) (18.62%), TB ascites (15.68%), peritoneal carcinomatosis (4.90%), hypothyroidism (2.94%), and liver metastases (0.98%) (Table 1). AFTP levels exceeded 2.5 gm/dl in 58% of individuals and fell below 2.5 gm/dl in 42% (Graph 1). SAAG levels exceeded 1.1 gm/dl in 65% of patients and fell below 1.1 gm/dl in 35% (Graph 2). SAAG levels were significantly associated with cirrhosis and congestive cardiac failure, but not with tuberculous ascites, hypothyroidism, peritoneal carcinomatosis ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2).

The average serum albumin was 2.89 ± 0.74 , ascitic fluid albumin was 1.41 ± 0.54 , AFTP was 2.49 ± 1.02 , and SAAG was 1.43 ± 0.657 (see Table 3). SAAG has a sensitivity of 86.22%, specificity of 85.78%, PPV of 95.36%, NPV of 67.12%, and diagnostic accuracy of 88.34%. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy of SAAG in relation to AFTP were all 65.74%, 62.32%, 32.76%, 86.20%, and 63%, respectively (Table 4).

Nephrotic syndrome accounted for 38% of the cases, followed by liver cirrhosis (22%), tuberculous ascites (20%), and cardiac ascites (16%), according to the research of Kondapalli CS et al. Ascitic fluid total protein (AFTP) had an accuracy rate of 78%, a positive predictive value of 89.2%, a negative predictive value of 46.2%, and a sensitivity of 60% at a 2.5 g/dL cut-off. distinguishing between "transudate" and "exudate" ascites. A serum ascites albumin gradient (SAAG) of 1.1 g/dL was able to accurately diagnose ascites as either "transudate" or "exudate" with a sensitivity of 47.5%, specificity of 80%, positive predictive value of 90.5%, negative predictive value of 27.6%, and overall accuracy of 54%.

Classifying ascites as 'high gradient' (due to Portal hypertension) or 'low gradient' (non-Portal) hypertensive conditions was achieved with a sensitivity of 100%, specificity of 93.5%, positive predictive value of 90.5%, negative predictive value of 100%, and accuracy of 96% using the serum ascites albumin gradient (SAAG) at 1.1 g/dL. A diagnosis accuracy of 100% for Nephrotic syndrome, 63.6% for Cirrhosis, 60% for tuberculous ascites, and 62.5% for Cardiac ascites was achieved using ascitic fluid total protein (AFTP) at 2.5 g/dL, regardless of whether the fluid was categorized as transudates or exudates. Whether it was categorized as High gradient or Low gradient ascites, the accuracy of the serum albumin gradient at 1.1 g/dL in detecting Nephrotic syndrome, Cirrhotic ascites, tuberculous ascites, and Cardiac ascites was 100% [9].

The sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and diagnostic accuracy for SAAG were 86.33%, 83.33%, and 86%, respectively, as reported by Gopi M et al. [10]. In contrast, for AFTP, the equivalent values were 60%, 60%, 27.27%, 85.71%, and 60%. The negative predictive value of AFTP was larger than that of SAAG, as reported by Rana SV et al. and Younas et al. [11,12].

Among 286 patients diagnosed with new-onset ascites, Subhani M et al. found that cirrhosis was present in 54.9% of cases, malignancy in 29.3%, and heart failure in 6.1% [13]. In order to identify the cause of ascites, Tiu DN et al. found that the SAAG value in patients with portal hypertension was 1.56 ± 0.37 gm/dl when comparing SAAG and AFTP levels. Sensitivity to SAAG was 93% and specificity was 87%, whereas AFTP was 73% and 60%, respectively. Because of its greater sensitivity and specificity, SAAG is a better measure to use than AFTP in cases with ascites [14].

The present study findings were similar to the above studies where SAAG was better than AFTP levels to determining the cause of the ascites. This study limitations in terms of minimal involvement of non-alcoholic cirrhosis cases. Further studies are

required to assess the accuracy of SAAG in non-alcoholic cirrhosis and also a marker for determining ascites.

Conclusion

The SAAG outperforms the conventional AFTP-based ascites classification system when it comes to determining the cause of the ascites. Study comparing SAAG with AFTP revealed that SAAG was more sensitive and specific in determining the underlying pathophysiology of ascites. Comparison of SAAG and AFTP's diagnostic accuracy revealed that SAAG significantly outperformed AFTP.

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